

Spectrophotometric Studies of Rhenium Complex with β -mercapto Cinnamic Acid

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The reagent β -mercapto cinnamic acid forms a stable reddish-brown colour with rhenium solution formed by reducing an aqueous solution of $KReO_4$ with stannous chloride in 0.5-1.25 *N* hydrochloric acid medium. The complex has no absorption maximum in the range 370-600 nm. At the arbitrarily chosen wavelength of 420 nm, the coloured solution obeys Beer's Law in the concentration range of 1-44 ppm of rhenium. Physicochemical studies indicate that the reagent forms 1 : 2 metal-ligand complex. The stability constant was determined by Leden and Rossotti's method and the log *K* values obtained are 10.90 and 10.45 respectively.

A number of organic thiocompounds¹⁻⁴ and oximes have been used for spectrophotometric determination of rhenium. Because of greater sensitivity of the reaction of Mo(VI) and W(VI) with many sulphur-bearing reagents, most of the methods require prior removal of these two metal ions. Though the toluene-3,4-dithiol method ($\epsilon = 2.34 \times 10^4$) has reasonable degree of precision and sensitivity, it is very much time consuming. There are some methods which do not give us all relevant information for a complete spectrophotometric study. In many methods, the composition of the complexes are not determined and very little is known about the overall stability constant and stepwise formation constants.

The present work describes the use of photometric determination of rhenium with β -mercapto cinnamic acid. Rhenium forms a reddish brown complex in 0.5-1.25 *N* HCl medium in presence of $SnCl_2$. Time needed for complete complex formation is very small and so the method is very rapid. The metal forms 1 : 2 complex as determined by Job's and molar ratio methods. The equilibrium constants have been evaluated by extending Leden's and Rossotti-Rossotti's methods by graphical extrapolation using spectrophotometric data.

The complex of rhenium with β -mercapto cinnamic acid is not extractable in common organic solvents.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz transmission cells was used.

The standard rhenium(VII) solution was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity of potassium perrhenate (Johnson Matthey) in double distilled water. The solution was standardised by Nitron method. A 0.4% (w/v) solution of β -mercapto cinnamic acid was prepared in absolute ethanol. 0.6694 *M* solution of stannous chloride (G. R., E. Merck) was prepared in 1 *N* hydrochloric

acid. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their chloride, sulphate or from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. All chemicals were of A.R. grade. Double distilled water was used for preparing the solutions.

Recommended procedure :

Absorbance curve : 4 ml of the β -mercapto cinnamic acid 0.4% (w/v) solution were added to a solution of perrhenate containing 2 ml of 0.25 mg/ml rhenium in a 25 ml volumetric flask, followed by 1 ml of 0.6694 *M* stannous chloride solution and hydrochloric acid to maintain the final normality of 0.96 *N*. This was diluted to 25 ml with the addition of measured quantity of dry ethanol and water in the ratio 2 : 1. This order was maintained throughout this work. The absorbance of the reddish brown complex thus formed was measured against a reagent blank similarly prepared and also that of the reagent against ethanol at different wavelengths. The system did not show any maximum absorption in the range 370-600 nm. Hence subsequent measurements were done at 420 nm.

Results and Discussion

The colour intensity remained constant even after 5 hrs. 2 ml of 0.4% reagent solution in absolute ethanol was quite enough for the full colour development of 20 ppm of rhenium. Addition of more reagent did not produce any adverse effect on the colour system. For subsequent measurements 4 ml of the reagent solution were found sufficient. For maximum colour development, 0.50 *N*-1.25 *N* HCl medium was required.

It has been observed that 1 ml of 0.6694 *M* Sn(II) chloride solution was sufficient for full colour development though a higher concentration of the latter had no adverse effect. A 0.6694 *M* $SnCl_2$ solution was therefore always used.

Validity of Beer's Law, relative error, sensitivity and molar absorptivity : Test solutions with different concentrations of rhenium were prepared by the

recommended procedure. The system was found to obey Beer's Law from 1-44 ppm. The Ringbom's⁵ optimal concentration range for measurement was found to be from 5.2 ppm-41.7 ppm. The relative error per 2% absolute photometric error⁶ was found to be 2.72. The molar absorptivity, as obtained from Beer's Law, is 4.82×10^3 at 420 nm and Sandell's sensitivity⁷ is $0.040 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

Composition of the complex: The ligand to metal ratio was determined by the method of Job⁸ and was found to be reproducible at different perchinate concentrations. Equimolar solutions ($5.37 \times 10^{-4} M$) of the metal ion and the reagent were mixed in complementary proportions of 6 ml, final volume being 25 ml. The metal to ligand ratio was found to be 1 : 2. The composition was further verified by molar ratio method. For a constant metal ion concentration $5.37 \times 10^{-4} M$, a plot of absorbance against increasing ligand concentration gave a break at metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2.

Effects of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions on the rhenium determination was studied by adding a definite amount of a foreign ion to a solution containing 20 ppm of rhenium and proceeding as under the recommended procedure. It was observed that rhenium can be determined in presence of 400 ppm of each of the ions like W^{6+} , UO_2^{2+} , V^{5+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Co^{2+} , oxalate, tartrate, citrate, EDTA (disodium salt), sulphate, acetate, chlorate, fluoride and thiocyanate. 200 ppm of Fe^{2+} are tolerated but Mo^{6+} , Cu^{2+} , titanium, platinum and nitrate ions interfered.

Stepwise formation constants: The procedure for evaluation of the stepwise formation constants was examined by proper extension of Leden's method and verified by the method of Rossotti-Rossotti.

Leden's method⁹: For evaluation of K_1 and K_2 we have assumed that the equilibrium concentrations of the ligand is equal to the total ligand concentrations. This assumption is found to be valid as is evident from the values of free ligand concentrations calculated for each determination of absorbances.

The successive stability values obtained by considering the degree of complexation are given below :

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \psi_1 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi - 1}{L} = \beta_1 = 1.6 \times 10^5$$

The plot of ψ_1 against free ligand concentration gave a straight line of intercept $\beta_1 = 1.6 \times 10^5$ (Fig. 1).

Similarly by substituting the value of β_1 in the following function :

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \psi_2 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi_1 - \beta_1}{L} = \beta_2 = 7.9 \times 10^{10}$$

Fig. 1. Leden's method of stability constant Re- β -mercapto cinnamic acid.

The plot of ψ_2 against free ligand concentration gave a straight line of intercept β_2 (Fig. 1), the overall stability constant. The values of K_1 and K_2 , are $K_1 = 1.6 \times 10^5$ and $K_2 = 4.93 \times 10^5$

Rossotti-Rossotti's method¹⁰: This method is based on the absorbance of a complex dependent on the total concentrations of ligand and central group. When only two complexes are formed, β_1 and β_2 may be calculated from the following equations :

$$\xi = \frac{A_S - \gamma \epsilon_L [L]}{C_M [L]} = \frac{\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1 \beta_1 [L]}{1 + \beta_1 [L]} \quad \dots (i)$$

$$\xi = \frac{A_S - \gamma \epsilon_L [L]}{C_M [L]} = \frac{\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1 \beta_1 [L] + \epsilon_2 \beta_2 [L]^2}{1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2} \quad \dots (ii)$$

where γ is the length of the optical path.

The plot of ξ against $\frac{\xi - \epsilon_0}{L}$ gave a straight line of slope $-\beta_1$ and intercept ϵ_1 for the complex.

The values of β_1 and ϵ_1 are found to be (Fig. 2.) $\beta_1 = 2.66 \times 10^5$ and $\epsilon_1 = 5.82 \times 10^3$. These values of β_1 and ϵ_1 were further substituted in equation (ii) which was solved as below :

$$\frac{\epsilon_0 - \xi}{\xi L} + \frac{\epsilon_1 - \xi \beta_1}{\xi L} = \beta_2 - \frac{\epsilon_2 \beta_2}{\xi} \quad \dots (iii)$$

The plot of $\frac{\epsilon_1 - \xi \beta_1}{\xi L} - \frac{1}{L}$ as ordinate and $1/\xi$ as abscissa gave straight line of slope $-\epsilon_2 \beta_2$ and intercept β_2 for the complex.

Fig. 2. Rossotti-Rossotti's method of stability constant Re- β -mercapto cinnamic acid.

The values of β_2 and ϵ_2 are found to be (Fig. 2.) $\beta_2 = 31.0 \times 10^9$ are $\epsilon_2 = 4.00 \times 10^8$.

The values of K_1 and K_2 are given below :

$$K_1 = 2.66 \times 10^5 ; K_2 = 1.17 \times 10^5$$

The values of overall stability constant obtained by Leden's method and Rossotti-Rossotti method are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANT AND STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEX AT 27°

Method	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log K_{Overall}
Leden	5.20	5.70	10.90
Rossotti-Rossotti	5.42	5.03	10.45

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